

Towards the Quality Measurement of Web Content Management System

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Abstract— In the last few year, the need of dynamic Webapp is grown up to create web pages on fly. A Content Management System will be used so frequently whenever a Webapp has significant content to be published. As the application grow in size and scope the web environment, traditional quality metrics become progressively more difficult to measure and manage. In this paper we try to found the various quality attributes and metrics for Content Management System(CMS).

Keywords— Content Management System (CMS), Metrics, Web Engineering, Quality

I. INTRODUCTION

Web 2.0 comes with the challenge of efficient web design that gives independence to share information in a user defined way. This enhances the creativity of user to devise innovative ways to collaborate. The way the information is currently being accessed may get change drastically in the coming years. The content management system tools have already started playing this role and their use in developing and maintaining the web sites is increasing day by day. This is mainly because of their ability to enable the companies to build, deploy and maintain highly dynamic internet, intranet and extranet web sites, quickly and efficiently.

Content Management System is a web application or set of applications, for easy creation of Web site and update and expansion. Managing the content and presentation of the site managed by CMS is prepared through a simple-to-use user interface. Usually it is a set of web pages containing complex forms and modules. As the size of web application is increasing, it is difficult to assess the quality of CMS because there are so many factors impact a CMS performance as it is a web application. Traditional quality metrics become progressively more difficult to measure and manage. There are many authors who define the quality metrics for web applications. In this paper we try to find out the various parameters of quality metrics for Content Management System.

II. CONTENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Content Management - is a set of processes and technologies that support the evolutionary life cycle of digital information. This digital information is often referred to as content or, to be precise, digital content. Digital content may take the form of text, such as documents, multimedia files, such as audio or video files, or any other file type which follows a content lifecycle which requires management.

Content Management System - A CMS is a tool that enables a variety of (centralised) technical and (decentralised) non technical staff to create, edit, manage and finally publish (in a number of formats) a variety of content (such as text, graphics, video, documents etc), whilst being constrained by a centralised set of rules, process and workflows that ensure coherent, validated electronic content.

TABLE I. MAJOR SYSTEM AND SUBSYSTEM OF CMS.

System	Sub-System
Collection System	Authoring System Conversion System Acquisition System Aggregation System Repository Interface
Management System	The Repository Versioning System Source Control System (Content and File Sharing) Localization System Workflow System CMS Administration System
Publishing System	Templating System Personalization System Deployment System Web System Print System E-mail System Syndication System Other Publication Systems Repository Interface

A. Types of content management systems:

The family of content management systems includes products with a common origins and similar names, but differ significantly in terms of offered functionality, which also results in a different internal structure. Depending on destination, CMS distinguishes among several types:

Web Content Management Systems (WCMS) - the most frequent type. These systems support creating web sites (portals, blogs, etc.) for all purposes.

Enterprise Content Management Systems (ECMS) – used by major institutions and developed countries. They offer technologies involved in the management, storage, safeguarding and sharing of content and supporting documents organizational processes.

Document Management Systems (DCMS) – intended mainly for the collection, sharing, and retrieval of various kinds of documents resulting in the company or from outside. Have the extensive search for documents by given criteria. Search is based on both subject matter documents, and so on. metadata.

Transactional Content Management System (TCMS) - These systems are used mostly in commercial environments such as stores. Facilitate the conduct transactions.

Integrated Content Management System (ICMS) – Aimed at simplifying collaboration between users and marketing documents.

Publications Content Management System (PCMS) - Applications for individuals, institutions using web portals as a place to publish books, articles or instructions.

Learning Content Management Systems (LCMS) -Model of these systems is based the combined elements of two systems: Content Management System (CMS) used to manage content and Learning Management System (LMS) for the management of players and process training. Applications of this type support to construct the pages with content and educational processes.

III. QUALITY METRICS FOR CMS

Software metric can define a standard way of measuring some attribute of the software development process, such as size, cost, defects, communications, difficulty or environment. Metrics can range from the primitive (directly measurable or countable, such as total number of outstanding defects) to complex and derived (such as number of non commented source statements per engineer per month).

By analyzing the metrics the organization the organization can take corrective action to fix those areas in the process, project or product which are the cause of the software defects. Quality metric data may be used to: spot trends in performance, compare alternatives, predict performance.

There the following attributes related to web CMS Quality.

- Usability
- Functionality
- Maintainability
- Security
- efficiency

A. Usability: Usability is defined as the degree to which something software, hardware or anything else is easy to use and good fit for the people who use it.

Usability should also be required in all stages of content management system. Storage of content and retrieval of content is more depends upon the individuals and group of users. The interface provided for the creation and authoring of content should be user interactive and should have aesthetic feature. There are the following attributes that define usability according to use of different groups of users of CMS.

- Understand ability
- Learn ability
- Explicitness
- Attractively
- Customisability
- Clarity
- Helpfulness
- User friendliness

B. Functionality: The degree to which the software satisfied stated needs as indicated by the following sub-

attributes: suitability, accuracy, interoperability, compliance and security.

A CMS provides the following capabilities and more for effectively managing and delivering functionality:

The CMS repository provides a place to store the code chunks that provide the functionality.

The CMS metadata facilities provide a way to tag functionality so that you can effectively store, locate, and select it for use in a particular page.

The CMS workflow system provides a way to wrap the functionality in a process for reviewing and approving it. The CMS templating system provides the capability to locate a particular chunk of functionality on a particular page based on the user, or any other criteria that you want to use to place information on a page. In addition, the templating system enables you to customize the user interface of the functionality based on rules that you design.

For the functionality measure for the CMS-it should have searching and retrieving capabilities, browsing and navigation features and application domain features.

C. Reliability: The amount of time that the web application is available for use, validate the user input and recovery.

There are following attributes that describe reliability of CMS:

C.1 Nondeficiency (or Maturity)

- C.1.1 Link errors
- C.1.2 Broken Links
- C.1.3 Invalid Links
- C.1.4 Unimplemented links
- C.1.5 Spelling Errors

C.2 Miscellaneous errors or drawbacks

- C.2.1 Deficiencies or absent features due to different browsers
- C.2.2 Deficiencies or unexpected results (such as nontrapped search errors, frame problems) independent of browser.
- C.2.3 Orphan pages
- C.2.4 Destination nodes (unexpectedly) undern construction

D. Efficiency: The degree to which the software makes optimal use of system resources. The efficiency of CMS can be measure by performance and accessibility of content.

D.1 Performance

- D.1.1 Quick static pages
- D.1.2 Display updated content.

D.2 Accessibility

- D.2.1 Information accessibility
- D.2.2 Support for text-only version
- D.2.3 Readability by deactivating the browser image feature
- D.2.4 Metadata information

E. Maintainability: Maintainability is the ease with which a program can be corrected if an error is

encountered, adapted if its environment changes, or enhanced if customer or user desires change in requirements. Maintainability can be measured by measuring some of the sub-characteristics of maintainability such as understand ability, analyzability, modifiability and testability.

Maintainability of CMS depends upon the ease of modification of content. Some of the CMS also provide facility of version control for content.

F. Security:

WCMSs are a desirable target for attackers. Once malicious users discover vulnerability in a particular WCMS, they can carry out attacks on many—if not all—of the applications built with it. Threats affect one or more security aspects. According to several experts says, Web application threats include

- Data manipulation. This type of attack violates data integrity, and the resulting data loss or perversion can have serious consequences. Common attack techniques here include parameter manipulation and SQL injection.
- Accessing confidential data. Here, attackers access off the- record data using techniques such as structured Query Language (SQL) injection and cross-site scripting (XSS).

- Phishing. This attack gathers confidential data—such as bank account information, social security numbers, or passwords—by contacting users under false pretences via email and luring them to Web sites where they're encouraged to enter personal data.

For example, attackers might use XSS to gather user data by placing manipulated input forms on pages managed by a WCMS. They can also exploit WCMS vulnerabilities to lure users to replicated Web sites that mimic an official site, such as a bank, and gather data accordingly.

- Code execution. Attackers can exploit WCMS vulnerabilities to load files or programs containing defective code onto a Web server. They can do this by using even simple graphic files. The WCMS must carefully verify inputs because such an attack can harm not only the WCMS itself, but also other applications on the same server.

- Spam. Here, Web crawlers scan the Internet for valid email addresses and send spam accordingly. Attackers can also use an application vulnerability to send spam through the application's server, turning it into a spam relay server.

To be considered secure, a Web application must ensure

- Authentication, by verifying that entities or people are who they pretend to be;
- Confidentiality, by hiding information from unauthorized people;
- Integrity, by preventing • unauthorized people from modifying, withholding, and deleting information; and
- Availability, by performing operations according to their purpose over time.

To achieve these goals, application developers can use several mechanisms, including sophisticated

authentication, user access control, and mechanisms that determine when to maintain data confidentiality, such as when not to show credit-card numbers when verifying a person's financial state.

Miller extends the above four quality attribute by adding the following attributes;

- Time
- Structure
- Content
- Accuracy and consistency
- Response time and latency

G. Time: How rapidly does the web CMS change? How do you highlight the changes? Have you done the version control on content. Which is the oldest content (mean the previous content)?

H. Structure: Structure is the way that you put information together. It encompasses the parts and pieces of a base of content and their relationships to each other. Structure is one of the basic qualities of content that you must understand and control in order to manage Content. If a content base is well structured, it has the following features,

- Its content divides into a set of well-defined categories (content type).
- Within each content type, the content segments into manageable chunks.(content component)
- Each content component chunk divides further into a well-defined set of parts (elements).
- Each element relates to other elements, from the same or another content component, by way of outlines, indexes, Cross-references and sequences.

I. Content: Content is the information and interactivity that organizations must harness in order to deliver value to their audiences. Content is rich information that you wrap in simple data. The quality of content is depend upon the storage and format of content.

- You must make format consistent across content categories, as well as across all content, in a single publication.
- You must separate format from content so that you can reuse the content in a variety of outputs.

J. Accuracy and consistency: Are today's copies of the pages downloaded the same as yesterday's? Close enough? Are the data presented accurately enough. Consistency among the content is very important in Web CMS. If the content is created in adaptive learning environment, then version control should be useful.

K. Response time and Latency: Does the web server respond to a browser request with in certain parameter. Is your application is provided the result in the specified time. In Web content management system, the result of search on content should be displayed on time, user does not have passions to wait for a long time.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Traditional quality metrics is not sufficient for the quality measure of Content Management system. There is need to find some more attribute related to CMS for quality measure. In this paper we tried to find the attributes of quality metrics for content management system. This is not exactly giving the attributes but by this we can identify the domain of related attributes. As a first step towards this goal, this paper proposes a set of attributes that should be taken into consideration during the evaluation of quality of CMS. Future work will be focused on the development of a model and methodology of total quality assessment of CMS as well as the empirical analysis of the importance of the proposed attributes and their relationships.

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